

GOVERNMENT MECHANISMS FOR PROMOTING INNOVATION IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract: In this article, the ways and means of state support for innovative activities in the service sector, the factors for the development of innovative activities, the economic meaning and essence of the use of innovative entrepreneurship in the service sector, various mechanisms and implementation methods of state regulation and support of innovative entrepreneurship are researched.

Key words: Innovative activity in the service sector, innovative entrepreneurship, innovative business, promotion of innovative activity, inventors, constructors, technologists.

INTRODUCTION: International experience shows that the systematic implementation of innovations that ensure qualitative growth in the service sector is the driving force of social development and economic development. Countries implementing innovative models of current economic development and "smart" technologies are achieving high success and have stable economic growth dynamics. As a result of the stable development of such countries, ensuring their competitiveness in the world markets is based on innovative developments and ideas, not on the basis of material production factors and labor resources.

The state support is being implemented in the transformation of the country into a stable market economy with a high share of innovation and intellectual contribution in the service sector of our republic, competitive services in the service market, and a favorable innovative investment environment. In the implementation of these goals, it is impossible to achieve without transitioning the economy of our republic to a fully innovative model, which requires the creation of an effective system of state support for innovative activities in the country and the promotion of the practical implementation of innovative ideas, developments and technologies in public administration, priority sectors of the economy, and the social sphere.

By the Decree of the Head of our State dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan", which approved the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 in seven priority areas, the accelerated development of the service sector, increasing the "role and share of services in the formation of gross domestic product, and fundamentally changing the structure of

provided services, primarily through their modern high-tech types,” was identified as one of the important directions¹.

Relevance and current status of the topic: Foreign scholars such as S.M. Yampolskiy², S.G. Galuza, V.I. Terexin, V.I. Shalun, Yu.A. Lvov, P. Samuelson, K.A. Raitskiy, T.V. Emelyanova, O.P. Efimova, and others have conducted research on the development of service enterprises and tourism, their technical and technological improvement, and increasing their efficiency.

During the years of independence, scholars of our country have also carried out a number of scientific studies on this topic. In particular, leading scientists such as M.Q. Pardaev, I. Ivatov, M.M. Mukhammadov, I.S. Tukhliyev, D.Kh. Aslanova³, O.A. Abdullaev, B.A. Abdukarimov, and T.S. Sharipov have addressed these issues and reflected their views in scientific literature.

At present, scientific research on improving service quality in service enterprises, enhancing their efficiency, and building competitiveness is being carried out at a rapid pace both in our country and abroad.

However, despite the wide scope of research conducted domestically and internationally on this topic, in our opinion, the work done specifically to improve the efficiency of service quality in enterprises is still insufficient.

Analysis and results. The development of innovative entrepreneurship in the service sector depends on many factors, the most important of which is the institutional environment. The role of the state in this process is of particular importance. Accordingly, the development of innovative activities in the service sector is determined by a number of circumstances. In our opinion, they are as follows: firstly, the lack of development of the relevant legal framework for the development and promotion of innovative activities in the service sector; secondly, the existence of problems in the field of access to investment resources; thirdly, the lack of improvement of the system of incentives for providing tax incentives aimed at supporting innovative activities in the field; fourthly, obstacles and shortcomings in the conditions for the implementation of innovative activities in the service sector; fifth, insufficient protection of the interests and rights of innovative entrepreneurs; sixth, insufficient development of the “innovative products (services) market”.

The importance of the state innovation policy is the objective characteristics of innovative processes, i.e. high level of risk, dependence on the level of development of the scientific environment and innovative infrastructure, large capital capacity for creating scientific research and experimental design work, opportunities for fair competition and wide development of entrepreneurship, innovations, scientific and technical personnel determined by high requirements for qualification⁴.

¹ Annex 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, “On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan,” — “Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022–2026 across Seven Priority Areas,” Lex.uz.

² Ямпольский С.М., Галуза С.Г. Экономические проблемы управления научно-техническим прогрессом. Киев: Наук.думка, 2010. С.364

³ Асланова Д.Х. Трудоёмкость продукции общественного питания и резервы её снижения: автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук. Киев. 2019-с.20.

⁴ Sh.S.Oltayev. Innovative ways of raising our country’s development to a new level by improving the quality of higher education (2024). *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 3(1), 258–263.

State support for innovative entrepreneurship is to create a favorable legal, tax and administrative environment for the activation of innovative entrepreneurship, creation of new jobs and improvement of living conditions among the population. The state innovation policy in relation to innovative business activity is a proportionate system of state regulation and support measures for innovative business, developed on the basis of the established goals and tasks, setting principles, various mechanisms and the creation of specialized state institutions.

Picture 1⁵

The active innovation policy of economic entities, manifested in the development of the production of radically new types of products and technologies , as well as in the expansion of local goods sales markets on this basis, ensures the growth of the gross domestic product, the development of scientific and technical potential, the formation of modern technical and technological structures in economic sectors and industries and allows to increase the competitiveness of products.

Currently, one of the important tasks is to transfer the economy of our republic from the direction of raw materials to the field of high-tech innovations. This allows to sharply increase the competitive potential of the country's economy by increasing its comparative advantages in the field of science, education and high technologies, and on this basis, to use new sources of economic growth and ensuring the well-being of the population.

The main directions of state regulation and support of innovative activities: The main directions of state regulation and support of innovative activities; Development of financial and credit mechanism; Improvement of analytical and information supply ; Development of personnel training system ; State policy to fight against monopoly aimed at development of competition ; Improvement of the tax system; Regulatory legal framework for the development of innovative activities.

The strategic goal of the concept of development of science until 2030 is to transition to an innovative and high-tech format of national economy development, to use and properly mobilize the competitive advantages of our country, to expand the volume of innovative products, to direct investments in areas that ensure rapid

⁵ Compiled by the author

economic growth, to increase the standard of living of the population several times. improvement, finding a scientific solution to current issues in the social sphere based on an innovative approach and scientific research and achieved results, developing scientific cooperation at the international level, as well as ensuring the implementation of the laws "On Science and Scientific Activity" and "On Innovative Activity"⁶.

In order to support and develop innovative activities in our republic, it is necessary to develop the concept of state regulation of innovative entrepreneurship in the service sector.

In our opinion, the unique aspect of this mechanism is that the leading place is given to enterprises and organizations in the field of service in the region. The mechanism is aimed at active participation in the implementation of business activities, takes into account its interests and is aimed at developing the demand for innovations by enterprises in the region. In a broad sense, this mechanism defines the directions for creating conditions for the development of initiatives and activities for its implementation - science and business cooperation.

The main goal of the organizational and economic mechanism of state regulation and support of innovative activity in the field of services and services is as follows: firstly, to provide the territory with new types of services due to the results of innovative activity; secondly, to stimulate the innovative activity of enterprises and organizations in the service sector of the region, to increase the competitiveness of services provided based on the results of scientific and technical activities; thirdly, legal regulation and protection of the interests of the subjects of innovative business activity in the service sector of the region; fourth, to create favorable conditions for the development of a competitive environment in the innovative sphere, as well as to support innovative and entrepreneurial structures in the region; fifth, formation of modern innovative infrastructure in the region; sixth, to ensure mutual cooperation of various elements of the regional innovation system through the development of the public-private partnership system.

Currently, the procedure for implementing innovative activities in service enterprises is at the stage of restructuring. Accordingly, the management of innovative projects is considered a shortcoming in the methodical provision of decision-making on their implementation. Based on this situation, it is necessary to develop a support system for innovative activities in modern service enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion, improvement of the main directions of development of innovative activity in modern service enterprises implies the implementation of the following measures:

✓ first, concentration on conducting scientific research within the framework of the important directions of the activities of enterprises and organizations in modern service industries;

✓ secondly, to attract small and private service enterprises to innovative activities based on the creation of technological roadmaps in the field;

⁶ Sh.S.Oltayev. Quality of Education In Higher Education Institutions of Our Country and Innovative Directions of Increasing Competitiveness. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 42, 253–256. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/2056>

- ✓ thirdly, purchase and sale of the results of innovative activities in order to stimulate innovative activity and increase economic efficiency in service enterprises with high scientific capacity;
- ✓ fourthly, to introduce methods and means of increasing the financial efficiency of innovative activities in service enterprises;
- ✓ fifth, application of means of optimizing the use of resources within the framework of the development of innovative entrepreneurship in service enterprises;
- ✓ sixth, directing resources to useful innovative projects based on the criteria determined by individuals or enterprises carrying out innovative activities.

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